

A PILOT STUDY ON SOCIO-DEMOGRAPHIC PROFILE AND LEVEL OF JOB SATISFACTION ON E-HRM PRACTICES AMONG THE SCHEDULED COMMERCIAL BANK EMPLOYEES

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Cite This Article: R. Padmaja & Dr. M. Rifaya Meera, "A Pilot Study on Socio-Demographic Profile and Level of Job Satisfaction on E-Hrm Practices among the Scheduled Commercial Bank Employees", International Journal of Interdisciplinary Research in Arts and Humanities, Volume 3, Issue 1, Page Number 364-368, 2018.

Abstract:

This paper aims to analyze the socio-demographic profile and the level of job satisfaction on electronic human resource management practices of the scheduled commercial bank employees in the Virudhunagar district. This study contains primary data alone which are collected for the pilot study. The researcher has used convenient sampling technique for the selection of the 160 sample respondents. Percentage analysis is used throughout the study. The researcher has applied the Chi-Square test by using of SPSS to test the relationship between socio-demographic profiles of the respondents such as gender, age, educational status, monthly income, and employment status, and their level of job satisfaction.

Key Words: E-HRM, Scheduled Commercial Banks, Job Satisfaction.

Introduction:

Human resource management (HRM) is the practice of recruiting, hiring, deploying and managing an organization's employees. HRM is often referred to simply as human resources (HR). A company or organization's HR department is usually responsible for creating, putting into effect and overseeing policies governing workers and the relationship of the organization with its employees. HRM is employee management with an emphasis on those employees as assets of the business. The modern HR technology term human capital management (HCM) has been used more frequently compared to the term HRM. The term HCM has had widespread adoption by large and midsize companies and other organizations of software to manage many HR functions.¹ E-HRM is the planning, implementation and application of information technology for both networking and supporting at least two individual or collective actors in their shared performing of HR activities (Strohmeier, S., 2007). E-HRM is in essence the devolution of HR functions to management and employees. They access these functions typically via intranet or other web-technology channels. The empowerment of managers and employees to perform certain chosen HR functions relieves the HR department of these tasks, allowing HR staff to focus less on the operational and more on the strategic elements of HR, and allowing organisations to lower HR department staffing levels as the administrative burden is lightened. It is anticipated that, as E-HRM develops and becomes more entrenched in business culture, these changes will become more apparent, but they have yet to be manifested to a significant degree (CIPD, 2007).

The introduction of technology based HRM to replace the initial paper based human resource systems came into lime line in the last decade due to the speedy development of the internet, which has enhanced the operation of electronic Human Resource Management. The internet has taken over majority of the functions of human resource practices in an organization globally. Consequently, organizations have started migrating from paper based human resource management to electronic human resource management practices in order to minimize cost and improve efficiency (Sylvester, Banidele & Olayemi, 2015).

In order for banks to operate in a global, highly competitive environment and utilise technological processes to drive improved efficiency, it is imperative that the traditional human resource management (HRM) processes are replaced with technology based electronic human resource management (E-HRM). Human Resource professionals in the banking industry need to rise to meet the increasing competition for experts in mobile talents, change in the composition, attitudes of personnel, change in employee/employer relationship as well as swift advances in human resource technology.

Skilled human resource experts in technological know-how capabilities, who are flexible and ready to compete in the fast and ever changing global technological workplace needed to be incorporated into the banking sector of the Indian economy. This would give rise to a new kind of business that would be based on diverse systems which would bring together the contributions of independent experts in a socially workable way. In today's Information Technology based economy, therefore, there is the need for banks to embrace the application of electronic human resource management practices in their operations. This is essential to meet up with the human resource challenges of the 21st century. Hence, this study surveyed the application of electronic human resource management practices on the job satisfaction among the SCB employees in Virudhunagar District.

Review of Literature:

Kettley and Reilly (2003) defined electronic human resource management as the application of conventional, web and voice technologies to enhance the administration, transactions, process and performance of human resources. Electronic human resource management has also been defined as the administrative support of the human resource function in organizations by using internet technology (Voermans & Veldhoven (2007). Strohmeier (2007) grasps electronic human resources management as the planning, implementation and application of data technology for both the networking and supporting of a minimum of two individuals in their collective performance of human resource activities. Electronic human resource management has also been viewed as an umbrella term that covers alllikely integrating mechanisms between human resource management and technological know-how which aim at creating value within and across organizations for targeted employees and management (Bondarouk, Ruel& Van der Heijden 2009). Marler and Fisher (2010) realizes electronic human resource management as the process of implementing human resource management strategies, policies and practices in organizations through the conscious use of channels supported by web technology. In general, electronic human resource management refers to an internet based tool used to systematize and sustain human resource processes.

The Study of Employee Satisfaction towards E-HRM System analysed the level of satisfaction of the employees working in National Capital Region of India primarily Delhi, Noida and Gurgoan. Data are collected from 182 sample respondents with the help of a well-structured interview schedule. Normality of the data was verified using skewness and kurtosis. The null hypotheses were framed. The hypotheses are tested using One Sample t-test, ANOVA and Chi – square. It was interpreted that there is a significant relationship between age, tenure, work experience and level of satisfaction of E-HRM for end users of selected organizations. There is no significant relationship between gender and E – HRM (Puja Sareen, 2015).

Objectives of the Study:

- To analyze the socio-demographic profile of the respondents.
- To identify the level of job satisfaction of the employees in the study area.
- To analyze the influences of profile of the customers on level of job satisfaction on the E-HRM Practices of the employees of SCB.

Hypothesis of the Study:

The following hypothesis is framed to fulfil the objectives of the present study.

- There is no significant relationship between socio-demographic variables and level of Job Satisfaction on E-HRM Practices of the SCB employees.

Methodology:

This study is both descriptive and analytical in nature and makes use of both primary and secondary data. The primary data have been collected from the bank employees with the help of questionnaire. The relevant secondary data have collected mainly through the database of the RBI and various standard text books, journal, magazine, websites, and so on. The researcher has used convenient sampling technique for the selection of the 160 sample respondents which is decided by using the software available in www.surveysystem.com. In order to analyze the primary data, the researcher has used statistical tools such as percentage analysis and chi-square test with the help of SPSS V.22 (Statistical Package for Social Sciences).

Results and Discussion:

The researcher has gathered socio-economic profile and demographic profile of the employees such as gender of the respondents, age of the respondents, marital status, area of residence, sector of bank, educational status of the respondents, monthly income of the respondents, cadre of employment of the respondents and year of experience. These details are presented in the succeeding pages.

Table 1: Gender of the Respondents

Gender	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Male	93	58.13
Female	67	41.88
Total	160.00	100.00

Source: SPSS output

Table 1 shows that out of 160 respondents, 58.13% of the respondents are male and the remaining 41.88% of the respondents are female.

Table 2: Age of the Respondents

Age	No. of Respondents	Percentage
18-30 years	44	27.50
31-40 years	36	22.50
41-50 years	35	21.88
Above 50 years	45	28.13
Total	160	100.00

Source: SPSS output

Out of 160 respondents, 44 (27.50 per cent) respondents are in the age group of 18 – 30 years of age, 36 respondents (22.50 per cent) are in the age group of 31 – 40 years, 35 respondents (21.88 per cent) belong to the age group of 41-50 years and the remaining 45 respondents (28.13 per cent) are in the age group of above 50 years.

Table 3: Marital Status of the Respondents

Marital Status	No .of Respondents	Percentage
Married	130	81.25
Unmarried	30	18.75
Total	160	100.00

Source: SPSS output

From the Table 3, it is inferred that out of 160 respondents, 130 respondents (81.25 per cent) are married, 30 respondents (18.75 per cent) are unmarried.

Table 4: Area of Residence

Area	No. of Residence	Percentage
Rural	39	24.38
Urban	51	31.87
Semi-urban	70	43.75
Total	160	100.00

Source: SPSS output

Table 4 vivid that out of 160 respondents, 39 employees are reside in rural area, 51 employees are live in the urban area and the remaining 70 respondents are reside in the semi-urban area.

Table 5: Educational Qualification

Educational Level	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Higher Secondary	32	20.00
Under Graduate	43	26.88
Post Graduate	60	37.50
Professional Course	25	15.63
Total	160	100.00

Source: SPSS output

Out of 160 respondents who are educated, 32 respondents (20.00 per cent) are educated up to higher secondary level; 43 respondents (26.88 per cent) are educated up to graduate level; 60 respondents (37.50 per cent) are educated up to post graduation and remaining 25 respondents (15.63 per cent) have completed the professional courses.

Table 6: Monthly Income of the Respondents

Income Level	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Upto Rs.20,000	13	08.13
Rs.20,001-Rs.30,000	55	34.38
Rs.30,001-Rs.40,000	25	15.63
Rs.40,001-Rs.50,000	29	18.13
Above Rs.50,000	38	23.75
Total	160	100.00

Source: SPSS output

Out of 160 respondents, 13 respondents (8.13 per cent) are having monthly income of Upto Rs.20,000; 55 respondents (34.38 per cent) are having monthly income of Rs. 20,001 – Rs. 30,000, 25 respondents (15.63 per cent) are having monthly income of Rs. 30,001 – Rs. 40,000, 29 respondents (18.13 per cent) are having monthly income of Rs.40,001 – Rs. 50,000 and the remaining 38 respondents (23.75 per cent) are having monthly income above Rs.50,000.

Table 7: Cadre of Employment

Cadre	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Sub-ordinate Staff	20	12.50
Clerk	40	25.00
Officer	33	20.63
Executive	11	06.88
Cash Officer	08	05.00
Special Assistant	02	01.25
Manager	12	07.50
Assistant Branch Manager	13	08.13
Assistant General Manager	13	08.13

General Manager	08	05.00
Total	160	100.00

Source: SPSS output

Out of 160 respondents, 20 employees are working in sub ordinate staff, 40 employees are clerk, 33 employees are officer cadre, 11 employees are executive officer, 8 employees are working on cashier, 2 employees are special assistant, 12 respondents are manager cadre, 13 employees are assistant branch manager, 13 employees are assistant general manager and the remaining 8 employees are working in general manager category.

Table 8: Years of Experience

Years	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Less than 5 years	35	21.88
6 years - 10 years	35	21.88
11 years - 15 years	52	32.50
More than 15 years	38	23.75
Total	160	100.00

Source: SPSS output

Out of 160 respondents, 35 employees are having less than 5 years of experience, 35 respondents are having 6-10 years of experience, 52 respondents are having 11-15 years of experience and the remaining 38 employees are having more than 15 years of experience in the field of banking.

Table 9: Sector of Bank

Sector	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Public sector	80	50.00
Private sector	80	50.00
Total	160	100.00

Source: SPSS output

Out of 160 respondents, 80 respondents are working in the public sector bank and the remaining 80 respondents are working in the private sector bank.

Identification of Level of Job Satisfaction:

For the purpose of computation of level of Job Satisfaction, the researcher has assigned the grades such as highly satisfied is 5, satisfied is 4, neutral is 3, dissatisfied is 2 and the strongly dissatisfied is 1. The level of job satisfaction is measured in the two levels, which are satisfied and dissatisfied. The respondents who have scored 60 i.e. (3 × 20) and above are comes under the category of satisfied and that whose score is below 60 have dissatisfied. The level of job satisfaction of 160 sample respondents is shown in Table 10.

Table 10: Level of Job Satisfaction

Level	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Satisfied	125	78.13
Dissatisfied	35	21.88
Total	160	100.00

Source: SPSS Computed Data

It has been observed that out of 160 respondents, 125 (78.13%) employees feel that satisfied their jobs and the remaining 35 (21.88%) employees say that the dissatisfied their jobs towards E-HRM Practices.

Socio-demographic profile and Level of Job Satisfaction on E-HRM Practices – Application of Chi-Square Test:

Chi-Square test is one of the simplest and mostly widely used non-parametric tests in statistical work. The researcher has used the Chi-Square test to test the relationship between socio-demographic profiles of the respondents such as gender, age, educational status, monthly income, employment status and their level of job satisfaction with the help of SPSS. Table 11 shows the chi-square test results of socio-demographic variables and the level of job satisfaction on E-HRM Practices.

Table 11: Socio-demographic Variables and Level of Job Satisfaction

Chi-Square Test Result

Particulars	Pearson Chi-Square Value	Hypothesis	Result
Gender and LoJS	0.521	Accepted	Not Significant
Age and LoJS	0.007	Rejected	Significant
Years of Experience and LoJS	0.010	Rejected	Significant

Source: SPSS Output – Computed Data Result

With regard to gender, the Chi-Square test result reveals that the Pearson Chi-Square Value is greater than the significant value of 0.05. So, the null hypothesis is accepted. Hence, there is no significant association between gender of the respondents and the level of job satisfaction. With regard to other variables, the Pearson's

Chi-Square Value is less than the significant value of 0.05. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected. Hence, it is concluded that there is significant association between socio-demographic variables such as age & years of experience and the level of job satisfaction on E-HRM Practices.

Conclusion:

Today's banking sector has been updated with information technology benefiting its customer and also providing a sophisticated environment to work for the employees. Based on the above findings, the researcher can conclude that banks have many e-HRM practices which applied in almost all banks in managing their human resources efficiently & effectively. The employees are highly satisfied with the E-HRM in their banks. When considering the overall E-HRM dimensions and socio-demographic variables, in selected public and private sector scheduled commercial banks employees job satisfaction on e-HRM practices are at a higher level in the study area.

References:

1. <https://searchhrsoftware.techtarget.com/definition/human-resource-management-HRM>
2. Strohmeier, S. (2007). Research in e-HRM: Review and implications. *Human Resource Management Review* 17(1), 19-37.
3. CIPD (2007). *A Barometer of HR Trends and Prospects*. London: CIPD
4. Sylvester, E. O., Bamidele, A. D. and Oluyemi, O. S. (2015). Implementing E-HRM System in Developing Countries: Challenges and Prospects. *International Journal of Applied Information Systems*, 9(8), 38-41.
5. Kettley, P. and Reilly, P. (2003). *E-HR: An Introduction*, IES Report 398. The Institute for Employment Studies,
6. Voermans, M. and Veldhoven, M. V. (2007). Attitude towards E-HRM: an empirical study at Philips. *Personnel Review*, 36(6), 887-902.
7. Strohmeier, S. (2007). Research in E-HRM: Review and implications. *Human resource management review*, 17(1), 19-37.
8. Bondarouk, T., Schilling, D. and Ruël, H. (2016). EHRM adoption in emerging economies: The case of subsidiaries of multinational corporations in Indonesia. *Canadian Journal of Administrative Sciences/Revue Canadienne des Sciences de Administration*, 33(2), 124-137.
9. Marler, J.H. and Fisher, S.L. (2010). An Evidence-Based Review of E-HRM and Strategic Human Resource Management, in 3rd European Academic Workshop on Electronic Human Resource Management Proceedings, 33-51.
10. Puja sareen. (2015). Study of Employee Satisfaction towards e-HRM system. *European Journal of Applied Business Management*, 1 (1), 01-18.